

ADVANCED COMPOSITES
Past Perspective and Future Strategy

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The impetus for the development of advanced composites was born out of the challenge that structural designers laid down to the materials development community in the 1950s and 1960s. That challenge was clearly performance dominated and involved primarily the need for combined high stiffness and strength with low density. This challenge has been tempered somewhat over recent years by increasing emphasis on cost, particularly life cycle cost, which includes cost of acquisition and cost of ownership.

The response of the metallics segment of the materials development community to advanced composites was to expend much effort on developments in materials such as aluminum and titanium. There has been some success but indeed the materials advances in these areas have been incremental. The overall impact of new alloys on aeronautical structures has consequently been for the most part limited and evolutionary in nature. Indeed, a forecast today would indicate little promise for major opportunities in the future to reduce acquisition cost and, with the exception of aluminum powder technology, not great promise for major increases in either static or, particularly, fatigue properties.

The materials and design community, therefore, turned to advanced composites as the major hope for dramatic improvements in structural efficiency. These involvements hold the promise, not only to provide the structural margins which have been eroded away in metals, but also to provide dramatic reductions in the weight of aeronautical structures. The non-metals community had, over the 1940s and 1950s, labored hard on the development of glass reinforced composites with considerable success in selected applications. These materials exhibited excellent strength-to-weight and fatigue properties and were and are being applied to the strength dominated portions of aeronautical structures. This is evidenced even in commercial aircraft where, for example, Boeing has increased the amount of glass composite structure used on their fleet of production aircraft starting in a major way with the 707s and proceeding to extensive usage on current 747s. This use has been dictated by both the opportunity to save weight and also the ability to display life cycle cost reductions with glass reinforced composites. These applications, however, are limited to non-flight safety critical structure and represent a relatively small fraction of the overall weight of an airplane. The major deficiency for glass composites is stiffness; a deficiency which is significant since much of the structure on most aircraft demands both strength and stiffness. The materials community therefore undertook the search for a filament which would possess both strength and stiffness and which would impart these characteristics to laminates. Boron fiber emerged as the first bright hope for such a filament in the early 1960s. Although the filament was identified early on as being difficult to produce at low cost, it was decided that development activities were warranted to determine if it was feasible to use these materials to replace glass reinforcements. Major emphasis was placed on the drive to see if first generation structures using boron filaments in conjunction with available epoxy matrices would perform up to design analysis predictions. These paper analysis predictions (many of which were initiated in a major Air Force assessment called PROJECT FORECAST conducted in 1963 and 1964) estimated dramatic weight savings on the order of 20-25% over metallic counterparts.

It should be made very clear that the early development years starting in 1965 and through the early 1970s were dominated by two major thrusts. The first was a considerable effort on filament reinforcement which started with boron and incorporated graphite as it emerged from research. This emphasis was dictated because without a high quality, reproducible filament the materials community had no answer to the designer's need for high stiffness structure. Indeed the preoccupation on filament negated any major activity on matrix development. This has been a major factor resulting in the situation today where the industry still uses essentially the same matrix materials as were available fifteen years ago.

The second major thrust was on structural components and this was the area where most of the resources available were utilized. There were early excursions

into aeropropulsion, re-entry vehicle, and helicopter rotor blade applications but clearly aeronautical application was selected as the major thrust. This was because of the major potential for significant application in all portions of the airframe and the resulting high payoff and major market that could result with success in this area. Interestingly, aeropropulsion activities have continued as have helicopter applications and these will be discussed later. After considerable analysis, the portion of the airplane that was initially selected was the empennage and the F-111 horizontal stabilizer was the first structures test bed. The criteria for selecting the horizontal stabilizer involved its relatively small size, simplicity, location in a weight sensitive portion of fighter aircraft and ease of inserting and removing it from the airplane. The strategy was to take limited resources and drive to not only a successful prototype demonstration but also to an early production commitment on the next U.S. airplane to reach production status. The F-111 horizontal stabilizer story is history now in that General Dynamics and the supporting materials industry was able to successfully develop, ground test and flight test an advanced composite full depth honeycomb horizontal stabilizer with approximately 25% weight saving over the production aluminum counterpart. Interestingly, the use of composites with honeycomb, which dominated much of the early design thinking, has changed to some degree now. An area of current major interest in this technology involves the ability to design highly efficient advanced composite structure without honeycomb to replace metallic honeycomb structural designs. There was another key element of the 1965 strategy that warrants discussion. This was the decision to seek secondary structure applications which could be flight tested while the horizontal stabilizer development was in progress. Items such as F-111 fixed wing trailing edge panels were designed, fabricated, ground tested and flight tested in the late 1960s. This flight test experience along with the successful F-111 horizontal stabilizer development lead to a production commitment by Grumman in 1970 to baseline boron/epoxy F-14 empennage structure. It should be noted that this decision was made by a company which had not participated in the F-111 composite stabilizer program. Indeed, Grumman was the company which made the production metal F-111 stabilizers for General Dynamics. Additionally, the first service to use the technology was not the Air Force, which did all of the development work, but the Navy. The most amazing aspect, however, involved the ability to move from finger size specimens in 1965 to a production commitment in 1970 on a major piece of flight safety critical structure for one of the highest performance airplanes ever designed and manufactured.

This success, theoretically, should have stimulated a rapid escalation in development resources and subsequent near term production commitment on wing and fuselage structure. The fact is it did not. There are numerous and complicated explanations (many of them fiscal) but the net result was that Air Force development continued at a more or less level pace. One of the major factors which gave management a reason to pause was the growing concern with the cost of our weapon systems. This emphasis on cost was to grow to major proportions in the mid- to late 1970s and is with us today. The cost of structure (particularly acquisition cost back then) was a new element in the equation. It is a fact that the F-14 stabilizers cost considerably more than a metal counterpart but use was dictated by the substantial weight savings (particularly in the aft end of the airplane where weight is critical). Since the weight/cost trades in wing and fuselage are not as attractive as in the empennage, high cost technology must be carefully analyzed to be sure that performance improvement warrants development and use. A second major factor was that wing and fuselage structure was significantly different from the full depth honeycomb structure used in fighter empennage. This made structural designers hesitant to press vigorously without substantial major development and validation. A third factor involved timing. The F-14 and F-15 provided major windows at the start of the 1970s but it would be difficult or impossible to retrofit composite wing and fuselage structure. Therefore, while there were empennage commitments on both of these airplanes, the windows for application of wing and fuselage structure had been missed. Major developmental investments had to be weighed against when a new system would be in development so that the technology could be used and a return on investment realized. There was,

however, a major immediate benefit derived from the successful stabilizer development and production use experience. This involved the stimulation of great interest and activity by the other services and NASA. There will be no attempt here to describe all of these activities since they are a matter of record but there are some observations that warrant discussion.

The Air Force development activity had been, and for that matter still is, focused primarily on the application of the technology to fighter aircraft. The advent of NASA activity starting in the early 1970s provided two major elements to the advanced composites development spectrum. The first is the involvement of the large aircraft industrial community in the United States. Boeing, Lockheed and McDonnell Douglas represent the community which makes all of the large transport aircraft (military and commercial) and are major contenders for strategic bomber aircraft development and production. The initial NASA activity involved structural development and flight test of large aircraft secondary structure. The second element involved the demonstration of the ability of this structure to obtain many more hours of flight time on commercial aircraft than ever could be achieved on military aircraft. Literally millions of hours have been accrued on advanced composite secondary structure as a result of NASA development efforts. This early NASA activity led to the ACEE (Aircraft Energy Efficiency) program which has expanded both secondary structure as well as empennage structure development with all three U.S. commercial airplane producers. I believe that the current major production use of composites on the new Boeing 767 and 757 airplanes directly stems from the NASA sponsored program. The Army has, coming off of Air Force development activities on Boeing Vertol CH-47 rotor blades, proceeded to explore both main and tail rotor application as well as major fuselage applications. Sikorsky, as a prime example, has not only made aggressive use of the technology in Army helicopters but has also introduced the technology into commercial helicopters. The Sikorsky S-76 Spirit uses advanced composites (predominantly glass and Kevlar) for over 60% of the exterior surface of the helicopter. This application includes major portions of the fuselage, upper deck fairings, horizontal stabilizer, etc., and results in a 30% weight savings in these airframe components. The Navy has, starting with the F-14, continued to be aggressive in use of the technology not only in the empennage area but also the first production use of the technology in wing skins on the F-18. The AV-8B program involves a major extended use of the technology incorporating the use of advanced composites in both the skins and substructure of a relatively large wing structure. This wing is aeroelastically tailored and, combined with a composite nose fuselage section, represents one of the most challenging and dramatic uses of the technology to date. The late 1978 flight date of the "all composite" AV-8B wing represents a major milestone in the development and demonstration of advanced composites technology in major structural airframe application. The AV-8B wing is twenty-eight feet long and represents a 20% weight savings which will contribute to doubling the range and payload of the aircraft.

It was clear to Air Force technology developers that the focus of development activities had to shift into an attack on wing and fuselage structure and life cycle cost. These two thrusts dominated the decade of the 1970s and indeed much of the other agency current production use can be traced back to Air Force development program efforts. A review of the structural activities would indicate several major programs worthy of note. The first involved the F-15 hybrid wing program conducted at McDonnell Douglas. This program represented the first major attack on cover/rib/spar structure as well as the first use of graphite fiber in developmental hardware. At that time, graphite had just started to emerge and offered bright hope of being the low cost reinforcement required to meet low acquisition cost objectives. On the F-15 wing, boron was used in the skins with selective use of graphite in the rib/spar substructure. This wing was successfully static tested in late 1974 and demonstrated approximately a 20% weight savings. However, due to the production stage of the F-15, it was not economically attractive to retrofit. The program, however, was a major ingredient in a later decision for McDonnell Douglas to press vigorously to the development and production use of graphite/epoxy in the F-15

speed brake in late 1975 as well as the late 1978 decision to proceed to make graphite/epoxy wing skins baseline on the F-18 program.

The second structures thrust to be noted involved the B-1 horizontal and vertical stabilizer development activities with Grumman and Rockwell, respectively. This development was characterized by being the first major large aircraft structural development activity and was aimed at possible B-1 production use as well as a major demonstration of cover/rib/spar structure typical of most aircraft wing structure designs. The program was conducted in parallel with the development of the baseline metal stabilizers which used aluminum skins with titanium substructure. The advanced composites approach on the horizontal stabilizer was to use graphite in the substructure and as the major ingredient in the skins. It should be noted that trade-off analyses indicated the need for selective use of boron to provide longitudinal stiffness and to aid in critical load transfer areas. It is anticipated that complex, highly loaded design situations in the future may also demand the selective use of a number of reinforcements in addition to graphite. The horizontal stabilizer was successfully static and fatigue tested in 1976 and demonstrated a 15%, or 500 pound, weight savings over the metal counterpart. This structure was the largest advanced composite component fabricated at that time (240 sq ft) and was projected to reflect approximately a 17-20% cost savings. For these reasons it was selected for baseline usage if the B-1 had proceeded to production. It is clear that this major development success also helped to pave the way for the designer confidence required in production decisions on the F-18 and AV-8B. A major facet to be noted is that advanced composite materials permitted a design that had 60% less substructure and consequently 46% fewer attachments. These advantages are typical of the design simplicity possible, which is a major factor in both the weight and cost savings, involved in the use of advanced composites.

The emphasis on the requirement for any new technology to be examined in terms of life cycle costs lead to the initiation of major Air Force initiatives which bridged the gap from the past to the present and which are key ingredients in our strategy for the future. A major ingredient in assessing development efforts involved the basic materials themselves. As pointed out previously, the reinforcement development initiatives in the 1960s involved boron to insure that a viable material was available for early structural development efforts. The introduction of graphite with cost projections as low as \$10 per pound or under gave great promise for low cost composite materials. The DuPont development of Kevlar (a potential \$10 per pound reinforcement) also promised a stable of reinforcements available to the structural designer with a range of properties and varying cost potential. Glass reinforcements were already available for less than \$2 per pound and had excellent tensile strength/density properties although less than optimum modulus or compression strength properties. Kevlar, a little more expensive, was a material with even better tensile strength/density properties and improved modulus/density over glass fibers but which also has less than optimum compression properties. High strength graphite reinforced composites had the best blend of low cost potential and good mechanical properties. Boron composites still possessed the best balance in terms of mechanical properties but the high cost of boron limited future use to selective applications which demanded the ultimate in mechanical properties, particularly modulus and compression strength. The DuPont initiative on Kevlar and the competition between major companies in the world for the graphite fiber market place lead to a decision for the Air Force to greatly reduce research and development activities on reinforcements in the mid-70s. Additionally, the sporting goods market place had stimulated the graphite producers to a competitive situation which resulted in substantial reductions in the price of graphite reinforcement. It should be noted that the sporting goods and non-aerospace market has diminished somewhat and, as we enter the 1980s, the advanced composite materials suppliers now look to aerospace manufacturers to be the major near term customers for their products. There is still great hope for non-aerospace markets to develop, particularly automotive, but most experts estimate this market will not develop until the mid- to late 1980s.

In any case there has been a substantial reduction in price on PAM based graphite fibers to the point where current prices on graphite reinforced tape are as low as \$35 per pound for relatively low volume orders. If one was to estimate the impact of inflation and factor in the stimulative potential of a significant increase in volume, it would reflect that the low price estimates for graphite fibers made in the early 1970s were not far off the mark. Union Carbide and Hercules are both in the process of major increases in facilities which will more than double current U.S. capacity which has produced 500,000 pounds per year. This increase in capacity bodes well for potential cost reductions to the \$10-15 per pound figure in the foreseeable future. These graphite cost reductions occurring in an environment where metal airframe materials costs have risen substantially as have lead times are a major factor in the current positive attitude by all airplane companies towards expanded use of advanced composites.

The downshift in development activities on reinforcements has been more than offset by a major escalation in matrix related development activities which have become a major determining factor in manufacturing processes in terms of improving reliability, quality and cost. The thrust of these matrix development activities will be described a little later.

The perspective on the strategy of the past and the current situation should provide valuable insight into our strategy for the future. It is clear that there are some major elements which, if properly developed and time phased, can result in the realization of the production use of advanced composites in major portions of both small and large airplane structures. The first element involves the development and validation of advanced design concepts which are based on advanced composites. Almost all applications discussed to date have reflected airplanes initially designed for metals in which composite designs have been developed and retrofitted. This approach has greatly inhibited both the performance and cost benefits available, particularly in the major load transfer areas such as wing to fuselage attachments. At this time, therefore, a major structural development program is underway at Northrop in which an advanced design airplane is being attacked in the wing to fuselage area using an all-up composite design approach. This concept includes a one piece wing, which uses an integrally co-cured lower skin substructure and a mechanically fastened upper skin, along with an all composite wing attached bulkhead and the use of filament wound inlet ducts. A major facet of the program will include a significant activity on durability testing of major structural elements and components to insure that full aircraft lifetime performance can be realized from all of these components individually as well as combined as an overall center fuselage and wing assembly. It is estimated that the data base realized from this program will establish the design confidence required to enable a fully composite designed airplane by the mid 1980s. This effort involves, and is closely coupled to, advanced materials and manufacturing initiatives which are geared to establishing the producibility and cost data base also required for production commitment.

The second major element involves life extension application to operating aircraft structures and trades on the excellent fatigue resistance of advanced composite structures. This capability has been graphically displayed time and time again. Indeed the successful CH-47 rotor blade development in the late 1960s had as one major objective, a test of the technology (at a very early stage of development) against one of the most rigorous and demanding environments in regard to fatigue and vibration. The imperviousness of advanced composites to corrosion is another attribute which makes the use of the technology advantageous from a maintenance standpoint as well. It must be understood, however, that there is not a wealth of data as yet from which any firm conclusions can be drawn. Data from the F-14 and F-15 experiences indicate, however, that major reductions in maintenance manhours can be achieved for advanced composites as compared to aluminum structure. This reduction in maintenance, combined with virtually unlimited life from a fatigue standpoint, makes retrofit a very attractive proposition to the logistics community. Indeed, at this juncture development activities are underway or being considered on C-141, T-38 and C-5 structure

all of which could lead to application of advanced composites and in many cases involve the use of composites to replace corrosion prone metallic honeycomb structures. The drive to use existing aircraft for much longer times than originally envisioned opens a number of other potential structural application opportunities. These opportunities can only be enhanced by the forecasted reductions in acquisition cost resulting from lower cost materials and improved fabrication processes. Initial data also indicate that repair of advanced composite structure can be readily accomplished, possibly even to a greater degree than metallic structure. For example, F-14 experience has demonstrated the ability to repair major damage which would have resulted in scrapping of metallic structure. A major technology issue still being rigorously pursued involves field inspection techniques which will be essential to enable broadened application of the technology.

The third major element of the strategy for the 1980s involves the design/engineering and manufacturing aspects of large aircraft structure. The weight reduction opportunities are extremely attractive to both military and commercial aircraft. Bomber and military transport aircraft can derive tremendous performance benefits from the 20-30% weight reduction potential. Additionally, commercial aircraft can derive substantial fuel savings benefits which are, and will continue to be, a crucial factor in the future of civil aviation. As previously discussed, NASA activities on secondary structure and empennage structure and Air Force efforts on the B-1 horizontal and vertical stabilizer have pioneered efforts toward large aircraft applications. There is no doubt, however, that additional efforts from a design and engineering standpoint are required in the immediate future to obtain the structural design confidence for both wing and fuselage structure for large aircraft. This is probably the major development program uncertainty existing at this time since neither the Air Force nor NASA have firmly committed to a development program. Such a program is a critical ingredient and recognition of the need and payoff hopefully will result in initiation of major activity in the early 1980s.

The materials and manufacturing initiatives which were initiated in the mid-1970s, when cost was identified as a significant factor, are the fourth and fifth major elements of the strategy for the 1980s. As was discussed earlier, the fabrication process and the matrix materials are key players in taking relatively expensive materials and converting them into low cost structural components. A facet of this situation which should not be overlooked involves the efficiency in materials usage to achieve final part configuration. Most metals, such as aluminum and titanium, must be extensively machined, resulting in the purchase of five to ten pounds of input material to get one useful pound of structure on the airplane. The resulting high cost of materials machining time and labor are major reasons for the high cost of metal airframe structure. Advanced composites technology by contrast uses a "build-up" approach which inherently results in much greater efficiency in materials usage with "buy to fly" ratios well under two to one.

The two major approaches in matrix development include a short term establishment of chemical composition specifications for existing matrix materials and a longer term development of easier to process matrices which will shorten and simplify the fabrication cycle as well as remove the need for expensive capital equipment investment. At this time chemical composition standards have been established and the first steps are being taken to validate equipment and procedures to monitor matrix material formulation and processing in production. This is a major step towards insuring reproducible, high quality structures emanating from the production floor. The second thrust is the development of new matrix materials. New matrix materials are being demonstrated such as the ATS (Acetylene Terminated Sulfone), which have long shelf life and which also are low flow/low pressure cure systems. The low pressure offers the possibility of vacuum bag, oven cure laminates which do not require the use of expensive autoclaves. These matrix materials are one part systems (no composition control required) which can be cured at 350 F and which have excellent moisture resistance. Advanced matrix materials such as these, used in conjunction with low cost reinforcements, offer

a potential breakthrough in terms of low cost structures fabrication with minimal capital equipment investment and energy utilization involved.

The fifth element involves the reduction of fabrication and assembly costs in the production of advanced composite structures. Activity in this area started in the mid-1970s also and a forecast for the 1980s indicates that this area is the key to the future for advanced composites. Almost all of the initial structures, and many of the present ones (even in production), were made by hand lay-up. Vigorous development activities from a manufacturing technology standpoint have resulted in such techniques as tape lay-up machines and the use of robots to mechanize the fabrication of advanced composite skins. These techniques are particularly adept at large area structures which have a relatively gentle contour such as stabilizer and wing skin structures. It has been established that techniques currently under development can lead to reductions on the order of 80% in factory hours with use of high speed lay-down, cutting and robotic transfer techniques. These procedures offer great promise for substantial cost reduction and will be in production use shortly on both F-16 and F-18 composite structures. A major opportunity for the future, however, is involved in co-curing of composite structure as was mentioned previously in the Northrop wing fuselage development program. The technique in which skin fabrication and cure is combined with substructure fabrication and assembly represents a major opportunity to dramatically reduce production floor operations and manhours. There have already been significant demonstrations of the viability of the concept but automation of complex production structural hardware has yet to be achieved. Another major facet of composite fabrication activities which will receive increasing emphasis in the future is the integrated composites fabrication center. There are several already in existence and several more in an advanced stage of development. One of the most advanced is the center at Grumman's Milledgeville, Georgia factory. At this facility automation is used to lay down tape, trim, inspect and ply stack for gently contoured hardware. This procedure has reduced the F-14 laminating cycle by 50%. Advanced lay-up and cutting machines at General Dynamics will accelerate fabrication capacity at General Dynamics from eight to forty-nine pounds per hour. Other center concepts involve the use of wide goods with high speed ply cutting, robotic transfer, automated materials handling equipment as well as continuous in-process inspection. All of these procedures are geared to current production opportunities. The major thrusts of the future will focus on combining automated skin fabrication with substructure fabrication and assembly and on manufacturing procedures for large, complex curvature structures typical of fuselage structures. These manufacturing initiatives will put into place the major missing elements required for automated manufacture of all candidate aircraft primary and secondary structural components. These integrated centers maximize the use of the computer and flexible automation which can revolutionize the ability to manufacture composite structures with tremendous gains in productivity. It is clear that such centers combined with Computer Integrated Centers for sheet metal, machining and assembly will form the backbone of the airplane structures "factory of the future."

The technology of advanced composites has been pursued relentlessly over the past twenty years, and has overcome and survived issues such as lightning strike, moisture resistance and graphite fiber conductivity. Objective review of the ability of composite structures to perform to date indicates outstanding success. The decade of the 1980s offers the great potential for this technology to move from limited usage on selected applications to broad, high payoff applications in a wide range of military and commercial aircraft. There is no doubt that there is great motivation for Government and industry, for materials/manufacturing and design engineers to press forward to exploit fully the advantages offered by this exciting technology. I firmly believe that vigorous pursuit of the strategy outlined will result in successful development and implementation of this revolutionary advance in airframe structures technology in the decade of the 1980s.